

Assessment of Cianjur Traditional Culinary (CTC) as an Ecotourism Product in Indonesia

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ABSTRACT

Traditional Culinary, potential as an ecotourism product, but this potential has not been realized by many parties in the effort to develop culinary ecotourism in the area of Cianjur Regency, West Java Province, Indonesia. This condition can be caused by the lack of attractiveness of the CTC and people's knowledge of the low Cianjur Traditional Culinary (CTC). This study aims to analyze the important values of CTC in the perspective/view of society. This activity is carried out through a test of culinary representation, which is a test to classify Cianjur traditional culinary based on the views /understanding of competent parties. The representation test was carried out by three groups of respondents, namely, Cianjur indigenous people/community leaders, Cianjur descendants, and non-Cianjur communities. The culinary type which is considered to be divided into three, namely, main food, snacks, and drinks includes aspects of social value, uniqueness, authenticity, scarcity, accessibility, and sensitivity. Data analysis uses one score one indicator scoring system with a Likert scale 1-7. The results of the study show that the CTC value is included in the rather low category (with an average value of 3.45). This condition occurs in each type of culinary group, although the value of the culinary type is higher than the snack and traditional Cianjur main food. CTC values, which are viewed from the uniqueness, scarcity, accessibility, sensitivity, social values/functions, and sensitivity, are categorized rather low on all types of culinary, so CTC has the potential to have a low selling value as an ecotourism product.

Keywords: Cianjur Traditional Culinary, Ecotourism product

INTRODUCTION

Tourism development by empowering culinary potential in Indonesia has enormous and strategic opportunities; this is supported by the large potential of its resources and markets. The potential of the number, types, and variations of Indonesian culinary is very much, although until now the data related to the types of culinary in Indonesia is not yet available properly. The market potential of culinary products is very

large if viewed from the level of tourist visits. The number of foreign tourist visits to Indonesia in 2013 reached 8,802,129 people (Kemendikbud 2014) with the expenditure level of tourists to meet culinary needs reaching 38.48% of total expenditure (Nurjaya *et al.* 2013). Indonesia also has many culinary varieties, but its development is felt to be still very weak and limited. The Ministry of Tourism and Creative Economy (Kemendikbud) in 2012 has developed

traditional culinary in Indonesia by determining 30 types of culinary. The number of culinary icons is considered still very low when compared to the traditional culinary wealth that exists with its various cultures. Traditional culinary is a variety of foods and drinks for certain people made from the main ingredients from the local area by using recipes from generation to generation according to the tastes of the community. Traditional food is formed because of the influence of environmental factors, socio-cultural, customs, ethnic groups, and beliefs (Marwanti 2000).

Cianjur as one of the districts in Indonesia has a large geographical and cultural potential and market in the development of traditional culinary ecotourism. However, until now this potential has not been fully utilized optimally. The limited information and development and marketing of various types of traditional culinary products that are suspected to be a factor in Cianjur Traditional Culinary (CTC) are not optimally developed. Until now, the number of variations of Cianjur Traditional Culinary products is not yet known in complete and reliable data. Traditional culinary information that is widely known to the public today is limited to a number of types of culinary that are still being marketed or still used in certain ceremonies. CTC's important value as a tourism product can be known based on several criteria, including uniqueness, scarcity, accessibility, sensitivity, and social function (Avenzora 2008), and originality.

MATERIALS & METHODS

Assessment of Cianjur Traditional Culinary is conducted in Cianjur Regency, West Java Province, Indonesia. This study is an advanced stage of the results of the CTC inventory that has been carried out. The results of the inventory of CTC types contained 171 types consisting of drinks (22 types), Snacks (76 types) and Main Foods (73 types), then tested the culinary representation. This test was conducted to

classify traditional Cianjur culinary based on the cultural views/understanding of competent parties. Variables assessing culinary products include social function, uniqueness, authenticity, scarcity, accessibility, and sensitivity.

Social aspects describe the potential of various social impacts in tourism activities. The uniqueness aspect illustrates the existence of CTC, the originality aspect ensures that the CTC provided is the result of the culture of the local community. The scarcity aspect shows the representation of CTC from other similar culinary products. The accessibility aspect shows the range of conditions and processes in providing CTC for tourists. Sensitivity aspects illustrate the influence of CTC on the sustainability of CTC itself and the surrounding environment.

Representation testing is done by presenting a list of culinary products and respondents are asked to state their knowledge of the product personally. Respondents consisted of indigenous people/communities of Cianjur, Cianjur descendants, and non-Cianjur communities. Tests for the representation of culinary products are carried out at least by three assessors in each respondent according to Avenzora (2008). The assessment criteria for each indicator in the instrument are made to represent value so that the overall indicator observed is the value of the culinary object under study (Avenzora 2008).

Determination of groups of respondents carried out with consideration of respondents is a market force in the development of traditional Cianjur culinary ecotourism. The determination of the respondent group was carried out with the assumption that it was able to provide real information about traditional culinary existence in accordance with the culture experienced by each respondent and was a potential market share in the marketing of culinary ecotourism. Respondents in the representation test are presented in Table 1.

Table 1 Criteria for Research Respondents

No	Respondent	Amount (people)	Criteria
1	Cianjur indigenous people/community leaders	6	Both parents Respondents are native people of Cianjur Born and raised in Cianjur Minimum age of 65 years Have knowledge / attention to Cianjur's Traditional Cuisine Understanding the cultural values of the community related to Cianjur cuisine
2	Cianjur descendants	23	One or both parents of the respondents were native to cianjur Born and raised in Cianjur Aged <50 years (teenager / adult) Have an interest in culinary
3	Non-Cianjur communities	14	The parents of the respondents are not Cianjur people. Born and raised outside the Cianjur district Aged <50 years (teenager / adult) Have an interest in culinary

Statistical Analysis

The study was carried out by distributing questionnaires in the form of close-ended patterns. The assessment used a scoring system (one score one indicator) with a Likert scale that is expanded to 1-7, in which the lowest value indicates the worst, and the highest indicates the best. Analysis

of the data used in the research was descriptive qualitative analysis with the stages of analysis, namely, data reduction, data presentation, and conclusion drawing. One score of one indicator system of data calculation formulae is the following equation :

$$p = \frac{(\sum R1 \times 1) + (\sum R2 \times 2) + (\sum R3 \times 3) + (\sum R4 \times 4) + (\sum R5 \times 5) + (\sum R6 \times 6) + (\sum R7 \times 7)}{\sum Rt}$$

Note: P = value of a parameter; $\sum R1-7$ = number of respondents who chose a scale score between 1 and 7; $\sum Rt$ = total number of the chosen respondents

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The results of the study show that the CTC value is included in the rather low category with an average value of 3.45. This condition occurs in each type of culinary group, although the value of the type of drinks culinary is higher than the snack and the main traditional Cianjur food as shown in Figure 1. The low level of tourist knowledge of the CTC turns out to be significant with the CTC value itself.

Roininen et al (2006) stated that the term local food is quite familiar to the public. Nearly 80% of the community respondents have sufficient knowledge of local food. The score of public knowledge on local/traditional food is 4-5 on a scale of 1 - 7. The public's view of the CTC value based on its type is not significantly different, although there is a tendency for drinks to be more widely known than other types of culinary. This is very possible considering the various types of drinks

which are the least compared to other cuisines as well as the experiences of the people who mostly consume these drinks in their daily lives.

Note: 1= Very Low; 2= Low; 3=Rather low; 4= Enough; 5= Rather high; 6= High; 7= Very high

Figure 1. Average CTC Values based on Culinary Type

One of the factors that influence the level of knowledge is changes in people's behavior. The results of the study by

Sempati and Lastariwati (2017) show that teenagers today have behaviors that are more likely to eat modern foods than traditional foods. According to Kotler & Armstrong (2008), consumer behavior is individuals, groups and organizations choose, buy, use and place goods, services, ideas or experiences to satisfy wants and needs. The results of the study show that the low CTC value, in general, does not reflect the low level of all aspects of the CTC itself, as presented in Figure 2.

Note: 1= Very Low; 2= Low; 3=Rather low; 4= Enough; 5= Rather high; 6= High; 7= Very high

Figure 2. CTC Value per Aspect of Assessment

Note: 1= Very Low; 2= Low; 3=Rather low; 4= Enough; 5= Rather high; 6= High; 7= Very high

Figure 3. CTC Values on Aspects per Type of Food

The low value of CTC is strongly influenced by the value of scarcity, the value of uniqueness, the social value, and accessibility of the CTC. Kuznesof *et al.* (1997) stated that the authenticity of a food

product must be maintained because the authenticity of food will affect the quality of traditional foods appearance. In accordance with the community assessment, the scarcity of CTC is included in the very low category (value 1.75), meaning that CTC is not a rare/limited product, but until now it is still found by many people. These conditions make people consider CTC, not an important product. This condition is supported by the results of the analysis that most CTC is the same as traditional culinary in the West Java region.

The community assessment of aspects of social value was also low because they lacked knowledge of CTC social values and functions that existed since long ago. Changes in the times resulted in people not using and knowing the CTC as much as ancient societies. CTC is only considered as an ingredient to fulfill physical needs and has no social value.

CTC accessibility is a supporting factor for the low value of CTC in the view of society. The results of the study in the native community stated that CTC was easily accessible, but the descendants and non-Cianjur people considered the CTC accessibility to be low. This condition is strongly influenced by the level of knowledge and needs of the community towards the CTC. The community has a low level of need for CTC which will affect the ignorance of the existence/availability of CTC. As is known, culinary needs are closely related to people's psychology, so it is only natural that indigenous people consider it still easy to access the CTC.

The CTC value in terms of sensitivity shows the value in the category is rather high with a value of 5.36. This condition shows that CTC is very suitable for consumption both physically and socially. CTC products as cultural products are very much in line with people's lives today.

The authenticity of Cianjur traditional culinary is included in the sufficient category with a value of 4.06. This is very reasonable considering that

most of CTC is a food that is also sold in other regions in West Java. This condition is due to Cianjur being one of the regions in West Java which is ethnically the same name the Sundanese. This ethnic similarity makes CTC mostly the same as the traditional culinary in West Java (Garjito 2013). However, it is likely that there will be a change in the form of culinary between regions with other regions for certain reasons. Pujileksono (2009) reveals that cultural changes can result in the loss of cultural elements that have ever existed, preserved cultural elements and the process of adaptation with new cultural elements. The assessment of Cianjur's Traditional Culinary Potential (CTC) from various aspects can be seen from each type of CTC. The type of CTC in question is the main food, snacks, and drinks. CTC values on aspects per type of food can be seen in Figure 3.

The sensitivity aspect is the aspect that has the highest value. CTC types that have the highest value on the sensitivity aspect are snacks with a value of 5.46 then the types of culinary drinks and main foods each worth 5.34 and 5.25. The authenticity aspect with the highest value for main food CTC types is 4.08 and CTC types of snacks and drinks with a value of 4.05 and 3.8. The third rank is the accessibility aspect with the highest CTC type value is a drink with a value of 4.74, then a type of culinary snack and the main meal which each has a value of 3.91 and 3.51. The 4th rank is the unique aspect with the highest CTC value which is the main food with a value of 3.32. The 5th rank is the social aspect with the highest CTC value, which is a drink worth 2.62. The last rating is the scarcity aspect with the highest CTC type, which is a drink worth 2.33.

Favalli *et al.* (2013) state that the uniqueness of products and food identities of consumers or buyers will affect the experience of consumers. Research conducted by Almlı *et al.* (2011) state that attributes of taste, health and food quality are the basis for a positive assessment of

traditional food, while prices and tastes are negative influences on the image of traditional food. Pieniak *et al.* (2009), reported that it was important that motivated European consumers to choose traditional foods because motives could control weight, compatibility, popularity (well-known), health aspects and natural content.

Mattiacci and Vignali (2004) emphasize the uniqueness of food will be a distinguishing factor and determinant of high food quality in the sense that producers can make food unique so that it can set a high price that will be followed by increasing profits. Furthermore, through the uniqueness of food, consumers will try to develop the concept of identity for food such as the concept of vegetarianism, organic food lovers, traditional food lovers and ethnic food lovers (Chambers *et al.* 2007)

Avermaete *et al.* (2004) argue that the uniqueness of traditional food is a fundamental factor in efforts to carry out development in rural areas. Furthermore, the uniqueness of food can be used as more value for producers and small and medium enterprises because of its unique nature. In the aspect of tourism, the uniqueness of food can be a driving force for visitors to visit places where unique foods are located (Mattiacci & Vignali 2004).

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the assessment, as an ecotourism product, it is known that there has been a cultural shift in society towards the CTC, which shows that the younger the Cianjur community the lower their level of knowledge of the CTC. The results of further research on CTC values (in terms of uniqueness, scarcity, accessibility, sensitivity, social values/functions, and sensitivity) turned out to be a rather low category for all types of culinary, so CTC has the potential to have a low selling value as an ecotourism product. Some aspects that result in low CTC values are due to the assumption that CTC is not a rare item, not unique and less socially

functioning.

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